

Solitary Malignant Mesothelioma of the Greater Omentum Mimicking Small Bowel GIST: A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Solitary malignant mesothelioma arising from the greater omentum is an exceptionally rare tumor and presents significant diagnostic challenges due to its clinical and radiological similarity to gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GIST) and other intra-abdominal malignancies. We present the case of a 72-year-old man with a history of treated pulmonary tuberculosis who was incidentally found to have a pelvic mass on computed tomography (CT), initially reported as an ileal GIST. He presented without abdominal pain, weight loss, or loss of appetite. Exploratory laparotomy revealed a solitary omental tumor attached to the greater omentum near the transverse colon, with no involvement of the small or large intestines or mesentery. Histopathology initially suggested moderately differentiated papillary adenocarcinoma, but second-opinion immunohistochemistry (IHC) confirmed a well-differentiated papillary mesothelial tumor (WDPMT), with CK7 and calretinin strong positivity, and negativity for GIST markers. The patient underwent complete surgical excision with an uneventful postoperative recovery, and the patient was discharged on the sixth postoperative day. Follow-up colonoscopy and endoscopy revealed no intraluminal lesion. He remains under oncological supervision for adjuvant chemotherapy. This case underscores the importance of considering localized omental mesothelioma in the differential diagnosis of intra-abdominal masses and highlights the pivotal role of histopathology with immunohistochemistry in distinguishing rare mesothelial tumors from more common abdominal neoplasms such as GIST.

KEYWORDS: Solitary, malignant, mesothelioma, omentum, well-differentiated papillary mesothelial tumor, gastrointestinal stromal tumor, immunohistochemistry, papillary adenocarcinoma, abdominal mass, histopathology, CK7, Calretinin.

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INTRODUCTION

Malignant mesothelioma is a rare tumor arising from mesothelial cells of the pleura, peritoneum, pericardium, or tunica vaginalis. While pleural mesothelioma accounts for the majority of cases, primary malignant mesothelioma of the greater omentum is extremely rare, with very few documented cases worldwide. Due to its unusual site of origin and nonspecific radiological features, it is often misdiagnosed as gastrointestinal or mesenteric neoplasms. When it arises as a solitary localized lesion, its clinical presentation is often misleading (1).

The greater omentum, commonly referred to as the "policeman of the abdomen," has important immunological and protective roles in abdominal pathology. Primary tumors of this structure are rare, and malignant mesothelioma confined to the omentum is a particularly unusual finding. Omental mesotheliomas usually present as diffuse peritoneal disease, but solitary localized omental lesions are seldom reported and represent a unique clinical and pathological entity (2).

In clinical practice, gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) are more commonly suspected when abdominal CT

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demonstrates an exophytic mass near the intestinal loops. This leads to diagnostic dilemmas, as seen in our patient who was initially thought to have an ileal loop GIST. Radiologically, intra-abdominal solitary mesotheliomas are frequently mistaken for GIST, sarcomas, or metastatic lesions (2). The diagnosis of mesothelioma can be further complicated by nonspecific histopathological features that may mimic papillary adenocarcinoma or other papillary neoplasms (3).

The histological subtypes of mesothelioma include epithelioid, sarcomatoid, biphasic, and well-differentiated papillary mesothelial tumor (WDPMT). WDPMT is considered a borderline tumor with lower malignant potential compared to diffuse malignant mesothelioma but requires careful follow-up due to the possibility of recurrence or malignant transformation. WDPMT is a recognized histological subtype of mesothelioma with papillary growth and often indolent behavior. However, localized WDPMT arising in the greater omentum is exceedingly rare, and its clinical significance remains uncertain due to limited case reports (4).

This report describes a case of solitary (localized) malignant mesothelioma of the greater omentum in a 72-year-old man, initially suspected as small bowel GIST, with final diagnosis confirmed by immunohistochemistry as WDPMT. The case highlights diagnostic pitfalls and the need for comprehensive pathological evaluation.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 72-year-old man was referred for further evaluation following an incidental finding on contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CECT) of the abdomen. He denied abdominal pain, weight loss, fever, or anorexia. Stool examination was positive for occult blood. His past medical history was significant for pulmonary tuberculosis, for which he had completed a six-month course of anti-tuberculosis therapy one year earlier.

On examination, his general condition was stable. He was afebrile, with blood pressure of 120/80 mmHg, pulse rate 86/min, and oxygen saturation 96% on room air. Chest auscultation revealed vesicular breath sounds with evidence of fibrosis consistent with healed tuberculosis. Abdominal examination showed a soft, non-tender abdomen without palpable mass.

Figure 1. USG abdomen showing a hypochoic lesion adjacent to the left lateral wall of the urinary bladder.

Laboratory investigations revealed hemoglobin 13.1 g/dL and markedly elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) of 110 mm/hr. Liver and renal function tests were normal. Viral serology was non-reactive. Echocardiography revealed normal cardiac chambers and valves with left ventricular ejection fraction of 71%. Chest X-ray demonstrated fibrotic changes of old Koch's lung.

Figure 2. Coronal and sagittal views of CECT abdomen showing a 4.5 × 4.6 × 5.0 cm homogeneously enhancing lobulated soft tissue mass in the left pelvis (red arrows).

USG abdomen showed a hypochoic lesion in the suprapubic area (SPA), measuring 4.7 × 4.0 × 4.7 cm, suggesting a soft tissue mass adjacent to the left lateral wall of the urinary bladder (Figure 1). CECT abdomen revealed a homogeneously enhancing lobulated exophytic soft tissue mass measuring 4.5 × 4.6 × 5.0 cm in the left pelvis, adjacent to the left lateral wall of the urinary bladder, appearing to arise from an ileal loop of small intestine (Figure 2, 3 & 4). Additionally, multiple hepatic and bilateral renal cysts were also noted. Based on radiological features, a diagnosis of ileal GIST was considered.

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Figure 3. Axial view of CECT abdomen (arterial phase) showing an ileal loop mass, suggestive of small bowel GIST (red arrow).

Figure 4. Axial view of CECT abdomen (porto-venous phase) showing an ileal loop mass, suggestive of small bowel GIST (red arrow).

Exploratory laparotomy revealed a 7 × 5.5 × 4 cm tumor attached to the greater omentum adjacent to the transverse colon (Figure 5). The small and large intestines were grossly normal with no evidence of intraluminal, mesenteric or peritoneal tumor. The tumor was completely excised along with the involved segment of omentum (Figure 6 & 7).

Figure 5. Intraoperative finding of greater omental tumor adjacent to the transverse colon.

Histopathology of the excised tumor initially showed moderately differentiated papillary adenocarcinoma, with no granulomatous inflammation and no features of GIST (Figure 8). A second opinion was obtained from Bumrungrad International Hospital, Thailand, where the lesion was reported as a papillary neoplasm with minute necrosis and dense lymphoplasmacytic infiltration (Figure 9).

Figure 6. Intraoperative view after complete resection of omental tumor and involved omentum.

Figure 7. Resected specimen of solitary greater omental tumor measuring 7 × 5.5 × 4 cm.

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Immunohistochemistry (IHC) revealed CK7 and calretinin strong positivity, CK20 and CDX2 negativity, TTF-1 negativity, CD117 (c-KIT) negativity, WT1 focal strong positivity, CK5/6 focal positivity, BAP1 negativity, MOC31 negativity, and PAX8 negativity. This confirmed the diagnosis of well-differentiated papillary mesothelial tumor (WDPMT) or diffuse malignant peritoneal mesothelioma with WDMP-like morphology and excluding GIST.

Figure 8. Gross section of tumour specimen with omental fat (16 x 5 x 4 cm).

Figure 9. Histopathological finding of malignant tumour arising from the greater omentum.

Figure 10. Upper GI endoscopy revealing normal gastric and duodenal mucosa.

Figure 11. Endoscopic images of the colon demonstrating normal mucosa.

The patient's postoperative recovery was uneventful. His diet was gradually progressed from liquids to solids, and wound healing was satisfactory. He was discharged on the sixth postoperative day in stable condition. At one-month follow-up, both upper GI endoscopy (Figure 10) and colonoscopy (Figure 11) revealed no intraluminal lesions. He remains under oncological follow-up for adjuvant chemotherapy.

DISCUSSION

Mesotheliomas are rare tumors, and primary omental mesothelioma is exceptionally rare, with very few reported cases. Involvement of the greater omentum is usually seen in diffuse peritoneal mesothelioma rather than as a solitary mass. Solitary or localized malignant mesothelioma of the greater omentum is a rare clinical entity, distinct from the more common diffuse peritoneal mesothelioma. Its rarity and nonspecific presentation often lead to misdiagnosis.

The initial radiological impression in this case was ileal GIST, reflecting the diagnostic challenge posed by omental tumors, which often mimic gastrointestinal neoplasms or metastatic carcinoma due to their close anatomical relationship with bowel loops. But intraoperative findings confirmed an omental origin. This underscores the importance of correlating intraoperative findings with histopathology.

Histologically, WDPMT can closely resemble papillary adenocarcinoma or other papillary tumors. Therefore, immunohistochemistry is crucial to establish the diagnosis. The presence of CK7 and calretinin positivity strongly supports mesothelial origin. Additional markers in this case (WT1, CK5/6 positivity; CK20, CDX2, TTF1, MOC31, PAX8 negativity) further exclude adenocarcinoma and GIST. BAP1 negativity is frequently seen in malignant mesotheliomas, adding further diagnostic support.

Risk factors for peritoneal mesothelioma include asbestos exposure, genetic susceptibility, and chronic peritoneal irritation. Our patient had no asbestos exposure history but

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did have a past history of tuberculosis. However, no clear association between tuberculosis and mesothelioma has been established.

Localized WDPMT is generally considered a low-grade neoplasm but reports of recurrence and progression to diffuse mesothelioma exist. Therefore, long-term surveillance is required (4).

Surgical excision remains the treatment of choice for localized WDPMT. Complete resection often leads to favorable outcomes. The role of adjuvant chemotherapy or HIPEC (hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy) is not well established but may be considered in cases with recurrence or residual disease.

Our case emphasizes diagnostic pitfalls when evaluating abdominal masses. Radiological findings may mimic GIST or metastatic carcinoma, but final diagnosis relies on histopathological and immunohistochemical confirmation. Early surgical intervention and histological verification are therefore critical. This case also underscores the importance of differentiating solitary localized omental mesothelioma from diffuse peritoneal mesothelioma. Unlike diffuse disease, localized tumors may be cured by complete excision, emphasizing the prognostic and therapeutic implications of accurate classification.

To our knowledge, this is among the few reported cases of solitary malignant greater omental mesothelioma diagnosed as WDPMT. Reporting such cases adds to the limited body of literature and may guide future diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

CONCLUSION

This case illustrates a rare presentation of solitary malignant mesothelioma of the greater omentum (WDPMT subtype), which was initially misdiagnosed as small bowel GIST on radiology. Definitive diagnosis required histopathology and immunohistochemistry, which revealed WDPMT. The patient underwent successful surgical excision with uneventful recovery and remains under oncological follow-up. This case highlights the need for a high index of suspicion and the indispensable role of IHC in evaluating unusual abdominal tumors.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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